

**On, for, and with practitioners –
Fostering transdisciplinary dissertations
in times of science criticism**

Academy Lecture, Issue XXXI
Daniel Perrin

This paper is a revised and extended version of the Academy Lecture given by Professor Daniel Perrin at the executive board meeting of the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences on 15 December 2023.

Fake news, conspiracy theories, and criticism of science and academia challenge democratic decision-making on societal levels. At the same time, the humanities and social sciences tend to experience both harsh criticism and dwindling funding. Against this backdrop, preparing next generations of scholars to mediate between the main discourses in sciences, professional fields outside academia, and society at large can both foster the scholars' individual success and bolster the standing of science in everyday life. This publication explains how – and to what effect – cooperation between Swiss universities has woven this rationale into a series of PhD programs in Applied Linguistics.

Les fake news, les théories du complot et les critiques à l'égard de la science représentent de grands défis pour la société et la prise de décision démocratique. Les sciences humaines et sociales en particulier subissent de virulentes critiques et une réduction des financements. Dans ce contexte, préparer les nouvelles générations de chercheuses et chercheurs à faire le lien entre les discours scientifiques pertinents, les domaines professionnels hors du monde académique et la société dans son ensemble peut à la fois favoriser leur réussite personnelle et renforcer le rôle de la science dans la vie quotidienne. La présente publication montre comment – et avec quel impact – ce principe, grâce à des initiatives conjointes réalisées par des universités suisses, a été introduit dans une série de programmes doctoraux en linguistique appliquée.

Fake News, Verschwörungstheorien und Kritik an Wissenschaft und Forschungsbetrieb fordern die Gesellschaft heraus bei der demokratischen Entscheidungsfindung. Zugleich sind die Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften scharfer Kritik und rückläufiger Finanzierung ausgesetzt. Das legt nahe, junge Forschende zu befähigen, zwischen den relevanten wissenschaftlichen Diskursen, den Berufsfeldern ausserhalb der akademischen Welt und der Gesellschaft als Ganzes zu vermitteln. Mit dieser Vermittlungsfähigkeit können Forschende ihre individuelle Position und die Rolle der Wissenschaft in der Gesellschaft stärken. Die vorliegende Publikation zeigt auf, wie – und mit welcher Wirkung – dieses Leitprinzip durch gemeinsame Initiativen Schweizer Hochschulen in einer Reihe von Doktoratsprogrammen in Angewandter Linguistik umgesetzt worden ist.

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Swiss Academy
of Humanities
and Social Sciences

IMPRINT

Publisher

Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences
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Proofreading and printing

Druck- und Werbebegleitung von Gunten, Köniz

Layout

Marie Steck, Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences

Cover Artwork

Lilian-Esther Krauthammer, Murg, Switzerland

1st edition, 2025 (200 printed copies)

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Citation

Perrin, Daniel (2025): On, for, and with practitioners – Fostering transdisciplinary dissertations in times of science criticism, ed. by the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences (Academy Lecture XXXI, Swiss Academies Communication 20,3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261812>

ISSN (Print): 2297-8275

ISSN (Online): 2297-184X

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261812>

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Foreword

Fake news, conspiracy theories, and criticism of science and academia challenge rational discourse and decision-making on societal levels. In academia, the humanities and social sciences tend to experience both harsh criticism and dwindling funding. Against this backdrop, systematically preparing next generations of scholars to mediate between the main discourses in sciences, professional fields outside academia, and society at large can both foster the scholars' individual success and bolster the standing of science in everyday life.

In this paper, I explain how – and to what effect – cooperative projects between Swiss universities have woven this rationale into a series of PhD programs in Applied Linguistics. Based on extended transdisciplinary project collaboration, we have developed a sequence of three PhD programs, each lasting four years, that enable students to combine disciplinary rigor with transdisciplinary impact. While the third program was still being evaluated for funding as this paper went to print, the first two accomplished programs demonstrate how their ambitious goals have been approached and achieved.

In the first part of the paper, I lay out our understanding of Applied Linguistics as reaching beyond academic disciplines and research frameworks. In the second part, I focus on the case of the digital literacy shift in public discourse as a prominent current topic in the field. Third, I outline how transdisciplinarity can contribute to understanding such phenomena. Fourth, I scale up from realizing transdisciplinary research projects to developing transdisciplinary PhD programs. Finally, I discuss the main characteristics of such programs as pitfalls and yet opportunities in times of disruption.

Introduction

In contemporary society, the proliferation of fake news, conspiracy theories, and widespread criticism of science and academia challenge rational discourse and decision-making processes. This issue is particularly pronounced within the humanities and social sciences, some of which tend to face both severe criticism and diminishing funding.ⁱ Against this backdrop, it makes sense to systematically prepare the next generation of scholars to mediate between the discourses within science, professional fields outside academia, and broader society.ⁱⁱ

Such preparation can be expected, on a micro level, to foster the forthcoming scholars' individual success in their scientific communities and beyond. On a macro level, it may contribute to strengthening the reputation of academia, science, and fact-based public discourse. On both levels, one of the prerequisites for success is a significant change in the way members of scientific communities are willing and able to understand socially relevant issues and contribute to sustainable solutions that are, in turn, understood and supported by society at large.

In this context, transdisciplinarity (TD) offers a promising research framework. TD aims to integrate knowledge from various disciplines. By doing so, it can address socially relevant issues across disciplinary boundaries. The main challenge with TD, however, is the dual burden it places on scholars' shoulders: transdisciplinary research requires both disciplinary rigor and the breadth to connect and communicate with stakeholders from other disciplines, professional fields outside academia, and society in all its diversity (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008; Sellberg, Cockburn, Holden, & Lam, 2021).

This is where Applied Linguistics (AL) comes in. With its focus on practical language and communication problems, it provides a suitable basis for implementing TD in doctoral education. Essentially, doing TD means translating and mediating between knowledge cultures, their epistemes, and their members' practices of using language to generate, scrutinize, and distribute knowledge. This interplay of language, knowledge, and mediation in intercultural settings is precisely what AL has been investigating and teaching for almost a century, long before TD emerged (Perrin & Kramsch, 2018).

The present paper elucidates how networked Swiss universities have incorporated transdisciplinary principles into their PhD programs in Applied Linguistics. The Zurich University of Applied Sciences focuses on research-based professional education while the Università della Svizzera italiana specializes

in developing innovative PhD programs. Together, the two universities have set up and run two transdisciplinary PhD programs.ⁱⁱⁱ For a third, forthcoming program, we have included two other universities in diverse linguistic regions.

The objective of this paper is to demonstrate how these programs have prepared students to balance disciplinary rigor and transdisciplinary impact (Sellberg et al., 2021) through intense project collaboration. The paper explains the rationale, development, implementation, and outcomes of these programs, highlighting their effectiveness in addressing contemporary challenges in public discourse and professional communication. It does so by taking the reader, in five steps and parts, from the PhD programs' context and foundations to the details of three exemplary theses:

- The first part lays out the understanding of Applied Linguistics as a field that extends beyond traditional academic boundaries.
- The second part focuses on the digital literacy shift in public discourse as a prominent object of current Applied Linguistics research.
- The third part outlines how transdisciplinary approaches can address such phenomena and make them better understood.
- The fourth part discusses the steps from conducting transdisciplinary research projects to implementing transdisciplinary PhD programs.
- The fifth part illustrates the intended key characteristics of the programs by drawing on exemplary PhD dissertations and their aftermaths.

The paper concludes by discussing transdisciplinary PhD programs, potential pitfalls and opportunities in times of societal disruption.

1. Research frameworks: Applied Linguistics and real-world language use

In traditional academic practice, PhD students are supervised by scholars rooted in specific academic fields and institutions. In our case, these are linguistics and Applied Linguistics (a) at public universities' departments of humanities and social sciences. Both universities involved in the first two PhD programs presented in this article share an interest in transdisciplinary collaboration (b) with the language industry (c) for the investigation of real-world language use (d). One of the departments is particularly experienced in extended ethnographies (e).

a) Applied Linguistics

Applied Linguistics (AL) is an inter- and transdisciplinary field that addresses practical problems related to language and communication. According to the International Association of Applied Linguistics, AILA (2024), AL is all about identifying, analyzing, and solving real-world issues through the application of linguistic theories and methodologies.^{iv} The field extends beyond traditional academic boundaries, engaging with sectors including education, healthcare, law, and business, to provide solutions that are both theoretically sound and practically viable.

In doing so, AL plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between theoretical research and practical applications. By addressing language issues that are intertwined with real-world problems ranging from global warming to political crises, AL contributes to the development of effective communication strategies in socially relevant contexts. This relevance to everyday issues makes AL an essential field in contemporary academia as well as at the interfaces of academia, non-academic professional fields, and society at large.

This broad understanding, promoted by AILA in its role as the field's global umbrella organization, reverberates in the mission statements of AILA's national affiliates. For example, the German association of AL aims to “bundle [...] activities and initiatives that focus on the research and optimization of communication processes in everyday life and in professional fields of application”.^v To give another example, the British association of AL includes “intercultural communication, political and commercial persuasion” and “the impact of new technologies” in its mission statement.^{vi}

In many academic cultures, however, AL is still considered the academic background of language learning and teaching only – or even as the field of teaching English as a foreign language. To give an example: to this day, the Chinese organization of Applied Linguistics terms itself CELEA, the acronym standing for “China English Language Education Association”. The same applies to JACET, the “Japan Association of College English Teachers”. Both organizations have widened their scope in the last two decades but not yet updated their names.

However, widening the scope is academically demanding. Not only do the agents in the field have to include a broader range of research foci and questions; they also need to grow their repertoires of methods and interactional practices. In other words: the interfaces with the outer world are becoming more complex. Addressing real-world issues outside the English language teaching classroom requires the awareness and knowledge to share one’s own interests and epistemes with neighboring fields and even fields outside academia. This is where transdisciplinarity comes in.

b) Transdisciplinarity

Transdisciplinarity (TD) is a research framework that reaches beyond disciplinary boundaries. Its origins can be traced back to a workshop organized by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in Nice, France, in 1970.^{vii} The workshop was entitled “Interdisciplinarity – Issues of education and research in universities”; its goal was to overcome the increasing alienation between academia and society. In his keynote and paper, the psychologist Jean Piaget called for a “total system without any firm boundaries between disciplines” (Piaget, 1972).

Since then, transgressing disciplinary boundaries, as outlined in Piaget’s programmatic paper, has resulted in two main conceptions of TD. Both understandings seek to overcome disciplinary boundaries, but they do so in two different yet related ways. In the first understanding (TD₁), transdisciplinarity aims to transcend the concept of discipline *within* academia as the sole principle for organizing and controlling academic knowledge. TD₁ argues for deep collaboration across and beyond academic disciplines and fields, such as AL and communication.

In the second understanding (TD₂), transdisciplinarity aims to transcend academia in general as the exclusive source of legitimate knowledge. As a result,

TD₂ argues for deep collaboration across and beyond academic and non-academic disciplines and fields. TD₂ research sees, for example, professionals in the fields of teaching or policymaking not only as the focus of research interests but also as participants and knowledge experts in the research process. Collaboration in TD₂ starts at the very beginning of a research project, when research questions are jointly formulated.

The essence of TD₂ lies in its ability to foster holistic understanding and comprehensive solutions (Pohl, 2024). By integrating insights from multiple disciplines and involving practitioners as partners on par, TD₂ ensures that research addresses the complexity of real-world issues from multiple socially relevant angles. In doing so, this collaborative approach not only enhances the relevance of academic research but also ensures its practical applicability. Combining the principles of AL and TD₂ enhances our ability to tackle complex societal issues in which language plays a crucial role.

With this in mind, the PhD programs discussed in this article build on an understanding of TD as TD₂. Such a research framework is particularly effective in tackling “wicked” real-world problems (Brown, Harris, & Russell, 2010) that require sustainable solutions, encompassing social, ecological, and economic dimensions (United Nations, 2015). In this sense, TD promotes collaboration with practitioners to co-create knowledge and develop interventions that are grounded in practical realities. It is “research on, for, and with” practitioners (Cameron, Frazer, Rampton, & Richardson, 1992, 22).

c) Language industry

Practitioners in the above sense include people in a variety of roles, such as professionals and members of society at large. Whereas society may be interested, for instance, in informed democratic decision-making, professionals often communicate to synchronize their collaborative value creation at work or to reach out to customers and other stakeholders. This applies to all industries; making and selling cheese or cars requires communication. Professionals in the language industry, however, create value mainly by producing language – their main products are communicational offers.

Globalization has broadened the scope of the communicational ties in both our personal and professional lives. Social and geographical mobility has increased, resulting in long-distance relationships and global markets. However, while en-

joying your holidays half-way around the world or consuming goods from far-flung places may be easy, thorough negotiation and deep understanding of one another's mindsets and cultures challenge participants' communicational skills. This is why intercultural communication has become a huge field of activity for the language industry.

But for every force there is a counterforce. Inevitably, widening social scopes is overlaid with narrowing them down at the same time. Globalization calls for localization, a dialectic termed *glocalization* (Khondker, 2004). It means that, for example, material products such as food and beverages sold worldwide need to be adapted for local markets in order to succeed. Similarly, semiotic products such as instruction manuals or conference keynotes not only have to be presented in a language the local addressees understand, but also in a style that meets their cultural expectations.

It goes without saying that the language industry has taken up this area of business. Be it the localization of an international advertising campaign or communication training for healthcare professionals from abroad – non-language professionals are offered communicational support by language professionals to cope with the dialectics of glocalization. This is why the language industry keeps both growing and diversifying. Taking language professionals' recent experience into account can benefit research in the intersection between TD and AL.

Since the rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI), language professionals' roles have seemed to be at stake. DeepL is a fast translator and ChatGPT writes superficially flawless texts. However, whether the results are fit for purpose in their cultural context needs to be checked by humans. Since the amount of automatically generated texts is skyrocketing,^{viii} the need for quality control at all levels is also rising sharply. Research has shown that AI has resulted in a disruptive shift, but this entails anything but a decline in services from the language industry (Angellone, Ehrensberger-Dow, & Massey, 2024).

d) The case of digital literacy

In this disruptive environment, digital literacy has become key to social participation. UNESCO (2023) defines literacy as a life-long continuum of learning and proficiency in reading, writing, and using numbers. Literacy as such, in this understanding, is a precondition for participation in both social and professional

contexts, as it has been for thousands of years (Figure 1). The shift from general literacy toward digital literacy involves understanding and navigating new modes of communication and information dissemination, which are often mediated by digital technologies and AI.

Figure 1. Innovations that have changed the way we write, think, and organize our societies

This shift presents both challenges and opportunities for enhancing literacy skills in the language industry itself, in all other professional domains, and in society at large. As communication moves from analog to digital environments, the ability to effectively navigate and critically utilize the related technologies becomes crucial. Of course, the shift not only includes individuals literacy skills but also transforms social systems such as education and public discourse. In doing so, it contributes to solving – and causing – wicked social problems such as growing digital gaps (e.g., Sanders & Scanlon, 2021).

In economy and finance, for example, knowing the difference between shares and bonds can help citizens invest their pension assets. Being able to read and understand the small print in a mortgage contract helps prevent buyers from being overambitious when looking for an apartment. And anticipating the risks associated with cryptocurrencies might protect individuals, companies, and pension funds from building masterplans on sand. In all these examples, financial literacy matters. How it interacts with writing in finance is the topic of Marlies Whitehouse’s PhD thesis (see Part 5.b).

The other two theses that serve as examples for our PhD programs in this article address aspects of digital literacy and writing as well: Marius Born’s thesis investigates situated activities of building trust in start-up communication. The temptations and pitfalls of playing with stakeholders’ flaws in digital literacy are identified. Dario D’Agostino focuses on practices in skeptical pandemic discourse, again in a context where the partial existence or lack of digital literacy results in addressees’ and multipliers’ (mis-)understanding of discursive patterns and key messages.

Its social relevance makes the digital literacy shift a “hot topic”^{ix} for research at the intersection between AL and TD. Deeply understanding “what works for whom under what circumstances” (Pawson & Tilley, 1997, 72) benefits from including all the relevant stakeholders as research partners. They bring their practical insights into the complex and dynamic practices of using language to construct the social world we live in. To this end, Applied Linguists tend to combine TD with ethnography and other established research frameworks when investigating writing and literacy.

e) Combining research frameworks to understand writing at work

Understanding real-life research objects such as digital literacy requires a multi-disciplinary approach. Therefore, when investigating professionals at work, scholars have combined AL and TD with frameworks such as Ethnography, Grounded Theory, Realist Social Theory, and Dynamic Systems Theory. Each framework offers insights into specific aspects of literacy and writing, from understanding participants’ views to explaining the emergence of patterns in big data. By combining these frameworks, researchers can develop a multi-perspective representation of their object of study.

Ethnography and Grounded Theory enable researchers to dig deep into the complexity of real-life cases. Ethnographers are open to the unexpected when they try to find out how the communities that they investigate think, feel, and behave. Ethnographies reflect on a community's sensemaking practices, for example, when participating in society with digital media. Grounded Theory can expand ethnographies by combining case studies in a procedure called theoretical sampling. Case by case, researchers use new data to challenge the previous findings and to further develop their data-based theory.

Transdisciplinarity considers practitioners co-researchers on par. They are experts in their practical knowledge and collaborate with the academic researchers throughout a project (see above, Part 1.b). This inclusive framework can facilitate ethnographers' access to workplaces such as media outlets, corporate newsrooms, and financial analysts' offices. TD research projects mostly include practical measures: action in the practical field under investigation, such as research-based coaching or organizational development. Hence the term *trans-disciplinary action research*.

Integrative social theories, such as Realist Social Theory, focus on the interplay between situated activity and social structures. In doing so, they help researchers explain how the observable is connected to enablements and constraints that cannot be accessed directly, such as individuals' beliefs or societies' taboos. Dynamic Systems Theory does so by focusing on non-linear change. Examples include unexpected writers' blocks, the sudden emergence of creative ideas, or the surprising acceptance or rejection of a new technology by professional communities or society at large.

Combining these frameworks (Figure 2) enables researchers to develop holistic and dynamic views of objects such as digital literacy and writing practices in the professions. The integrated approach allows for a deeper understanding of how situated activity interacts with layered contexts such as individual repertoires, organizational resources, and social and technological advancements. In forerunner projects of our PhD school series, we used this approach to analyze the long-term developments of literacy and writing in the domain of journalism and public discourse.

	EG Ethnography	GT Grounded Theory	TDA Transdisciplinary Action Research	RST Realist Social Theory	DST Dynamic Systems Theory
Focus	case study	+ generalization	+ real-world problem	+ social relevance	+ dynamics
Outcome	understanding communities' perspectives	building theories by coding data in cycles	solving the problem with practitioners	contextualizing situated activity in the real world	explaining emergence in big data

Figure 2. Combining research frameworks in Applied Linguistics

2. Research focus: The example of the digital literacy shift in public discourse

Real-world language use in daily life and the professions has been evolving at a fast pace in light of digital technologies since the 1980s and AI since the 2020s. This has resulted in a shift in text production patterns (a) from *focused writing* to what we have termed *writing by-the-way* (c). PhD research in a forerunner of our programs has analyzed such patterns by segmenting writing activities across timespans in scalable phases that are dominated by specific types of activity (d). On a macro level, such an analysis has revealed a five-phase shift in journalistic text production (e).

a) Text production in the professions

Text production practices in professional settings vary widely. From a functional perspective, they range from highly routinized to more emergent and socially creative (Foucault, 1966; Bourdieu, 1977; Hanks, 1996; Bhatia, 2008; Pennycook, 2010; and Perrin, 2013a). However, in contrast to sheer routines on the one hand and unpredictable behavior on the other, practices are conscious to a certain extent and subject to intentional change. They are shared by communities of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991) and meant to improve with growing expertise throughout professional life.

From a context perspective, practices interact with external factors such as the roles and expertise of the individuals involved, the organizational environment, and the cultural and historical backdrop. Role and expertise are often closely connected; experienced writers dispose of wider and deeper repertoires of practices, which helps them master more complex and dynamic tasks and advance in the field. The context in which texts are produced includes the respective tools, from pens to AI networks. The cultural and historical backdrop interacts with norms surrounding text production.

Furthermore, practices are embodied, multi-semiotic, and mediatized. This means that they include bodily subtasks such as punching the keys while writing or breathing consciously when speaking in public. Such practices always generate traces in several semiotic systems; for example, speaking includes body language, too, and writing activities like punching the keys can be audible. Most text production practices are effectuated by and interact with media such as

computers or pen and paper, and result in products that are spoken, written, or gestured.

From a structural perspective, real-life practices never come alone but are organized in sequences and networks. Sequences of practices include, for example, opening a new file on the computer, setting the text parameters, and only then starting to write. Networks combine practices that take place (quasi-)simultaneously and interact at their nodes, for instance adjusting verbal linking devices such as conjunctions while changing the order of phrases and sentences. This also shows that the concept of practice is recursive: *practices* can include (sub-)practices.

Understanding these characteristics of practices is essential for fostering literacy. First, it sharpens the lens through which research can spot variation and change in practices in the short and long term. Second, it fosters data-based and transparent analyses of problems in activity fields such as professional text production; questionable practices can be considered the observable surface of incompatible social and organizational structures. And third, it helps develop effective interventions for the improvement of text production practices in professional settings.

b) Typologies of text production processes

Research on text production in the professions has long aimed at classifying writing processes. Results of such attempts are types and typologies. Prominent examples include “writing signatures” (Levy & Ransdell, 1996). This open typology is based on the idea that every writer develops their own individual, signature-like behavioral pattern of managing most of their writing processes. For each new process a single writer commences, some characteristics remain constant, no matter the task or the circumstances. In this typology, there are as many types as there are writers.

Another widespread but closed typology distinguishes between a “knowledge telling” and a “knowledge transforming” pattern (Scardamalia & Bereiter, 1987). The core idea here is ontogenetical: when children learn to write, they first tell their stories from top to bottom, in one go. Only after understanding the difference between ephemeral speaking and revisable writing do they begin to modify their emerging texts. They have then realized that they can transform narrative knowledge into consciously organized texts that do not have to follow the and-then order of oral contributions.

A phylogenetical typology, by contrast, differentiates between types of writing related to eras of our species' socio-historical development. Writing types are conceived of as resulting from writers' enablements and constraints in specific segments of human history. In medieval Europe, for example, writing can be characterized as having been calligraphic, in contrast to a “maschinelle Konzeption”, a machine conception of writing in the era of book printing and the fast spread of literacy (Ludwig, 2005). Recent complementary types include digital writing of fluid texts on screens and writing as promoting AI.

Typologies based on macro-segments of time, such as the one above, are quite rare in research on writing and text production. In contrast, typologies based on micro-segments within the timespan of a writing process are numerous. Starting from laboratory experiments in psychology, researchers have identified phase-related activity types of writing such as planning, formulating, and reviewing (Hayes & Flower, 1987). Later examples of such typologies include activities that characterize writing outside the lab in real-life contexts such as workplaces (Perrin, 2003).

In between the macro level of human history and the micro level of a single text production process or a single utterance, typologies can focus on the development of writing in a domain, such as a profession, over decades. An example of such a meso-level typology differentiates between “focused writing” and “writing by-the-way” (Hicks & Perrin, 2014). As always with dichotomic typologies of real-life phenomena, the two types are poles of a continuum, meant for analytic purposes. This typology is intended to facilitate a better understanding of change in a professional field.

c) Focused writing and writing by-the-way

Focused writing involves intentional, coherent, and often solitary efforts to produce high-quality texts. This traditional mode of writing is typically carried out in a quiet and controlled environment. It facilitates deep reflection and meticulous editing. Focused writing is characterized by its separation from immediate context, allowing writers to craft near-perfect communicational offerings. “Unlike speech, [the result of focused writing] is decoupled from traces of fighting with thoughts and words – a close-to-perfect communicational offer.” (Hicks & Perrin, 2014, 231)

Focused writing has long been the standard in professional and academic contexts. Its emphasis on thoroughness and precision makes it ideal for producing well-crafted, detailed documents. From dissertations to strategy papers, written work can be much more than prefabricated thoughts written down: it is both the result and the starting point of writers' intense thinking as they watch their text emerge and rearrange the pieces both in their minds and on the screen. This close interaction of writing and thinking has been termed “epistemic writing” (Molitor-Lübbert, 2002).

However, the demands of modern communication, with its emphasis on speed and adaptability, have challenged this traditional mode of writing. In contrast to focused writing, writing by-the-way is ubiquitous, fragmented, and socially dialogic. This mode of writing reflects the dynamic nature of contemporary communication, where people use digital, mobile, and connected media to synchronize knowledge, share emotions, and maintain identities continuously throughout the day (Hicks & Perrin, 2014).

Writing by-the-way, therefore, represents a significant shift in how texts are produced and consumed. Being more spontaneous and responsive, it reflects the immediacy and interconnectedness of digital communication. On the flipside, the results of writing by-the-way inevitably lack the thoroughness of a focused piece. Like oral contributions, they often depend on an ephemeral context to make sense to their target audience. Understanding the dynamics of writing by-the-way is crucial for developing strategies to manage and utilize this mode of writing effectively.

With social media, writing by-the-way has increased so much that writing has replaced speaking as the default mode of communication in many domains (Brandt, 2014). In academia, it has become a relevant driver of success at the interfaces to society at large (e.g., Hyland, 2024). Yet, it is important to remember that the dichotomy of focused writing and writing by-the-way is an analytical tool marking the ends of a continuum. In real-life text production, the two types often mix or alternate, depending on the phase within a text production process.

d) Writing phases

Writing processes can be divided into phases in which certain types of activity (see Part 2.b) predominate (Figure 3). The phases vary in scale, from lasting a few seconds while authors revise a formulation, up to hours when they draft an

entire book chapter, and even to decades in writers' lifespans and centuries in human history. The interplay of these layered timeframes has been investigated in the framework of Dynamic Systems Theory (e.g., Fürer, 2017) and shown to influence – and be influenced by – cultural, biographical, and textual factors.

Figure 3. The helix of activity fields that interact in writing processes

- Cultural and biographical factors range from the distribution of literacy in a society to the access among certain communities to certain writing tools. In the last century, most people's first biographical phase of writing was dominated by handwriting before they learned to use typewriters in their professional education or at school in higher grades. Many children born today not only read and write, from the very beginning, on digital devices, but also in an environment of social media and artificial intelligence. Thus, their first phase of literacy already includes or is dominated by writing by-the-way.
- Textual factors include, for example, the writing task, any source texts, and the new text written so far. Within a text production process, the writers' focus of attention can shift back and forth between comprehending the task, reading any source texts, and re-reading their own emerging text. With new predominant activities, new phases begin. Some writers tend to consciously

start their text production processes with phases in which they set their goal, then they plan and write the text, revise it if necessary, and implement the final product. Others oscillate between these practices.

Such differences in managing text production phases have been shown to be individual but also related to writers' expertise (Perrin, 2013c). For example, highly experienced writers across domains tend to be able to plan both their writing processes and the text products more thoroughly and, at the same time, more flexibly than their less experienced colleagues. By following a flexible master plan, they avoid investing time in dead ends in an emerging text but remain open to the unexpected while writing and can easily adapt their plan at low cost on the go (Perrin, 2016).

The concept of writing phases highlights the complexity and fluidity of writing processes. Recognizing these phases can help writers and educators develop more effective strategies for managing and supporting writing activities. By understanding the different phases of writing, TD researchers can develop interventions as well as tailor them to address specific challenges and optimize the writing process. This applies not only to the phases within a certain writing process, but also, on larger scales and over longer timeframes, to the phases a profession and its writers go through.

e) The five-phase shift in mediatized public discourse

The evolution of writing in digital journalism provides an example of the digital literacy shift in a profession highly involved with public discourse. This shift can be understood as a sequence of five phases. As is often the case in real-life processes, the activities that dominate a phase overlap, leading to smooth transitions. Therefore, while there is a prototypical core to each phase, it remains disputable where exactly a phase begins and ends. The following description shows the extent to which writing practices and contexts interact and change together in a professional field.

In the 1990s, journalism replicated production patterns from print and broadcasting when producing media items for the Internet. Besides including hyperlinks from time to time, both the writing processes and the emerging text products were organized along the patterns of focused writing. This changed to a degree in the 2000s, when the accelerated rise of the Internet changed the practices of journalistic research. Doing research on the fly and by-the-way had

become much easier. Therefore, focused writing was interspersed with browsing the Internet from time to time.

In the 2010s, social media communities began to both trigger and comment on journalistic content. In response, journalists used social media before and during the writing process to get stimuli from their audience and sources, which resulted in follow-up contributions on topics in public media. Moreover, journalists found themselves exposed to publicly accessible acceptance scores (likes) and orchestrated verbal criticism. Therefore, in the 2020s, journalists started to fiercely engage in community management, further merging focused writing and writing by-the-way.

Since 2023, big data and tools driven by artificial intelligence have influenced writing practices in public discourse. Journalists and media companies have been using AI tools increasingly to perform semi-automated research in large amounts of data (data journalism) but also to write and illustrate articles for digital print, audio, and video media. For many journalists, their core activity has shifted toward pre-editing and post-editing automatically generated text. This requires a completely different mindset than focused writing did before digitalization.

This five-phase shift illustrates how technological advancements and changing communication practices have transformed the literacy profile and the production practices in a domain that makes such a crucial contribution to public discourse. Each phase represents a substantial change in how writers produce and interact with content and context. Understanding the shift is essential for developing strategies to master the changes in professional writing practices. This makes the digital literacy shift an ideal starting point for transdisciplinary research in Applied Linguistics.

3. Methodology: Investigating writing at work in multi-layered contexts

Analyzing real-life phenomena, such as the digital literacy shift, requires multi-method approaches that grant access to all the relevant levels of language use – from the social construction of meaning to individuals’ language production and reflection (a). The methods combined often transgress research cultures and their methodological traditions (b). In the projects that served as a starting point for our PhD school, we combined the French tradition of Genetic Criticism (c) with a German approach to text production research (d) in an approach we termed *Progression Analysis* (e).

a) International interest in everyday language reflection

Over the last decades, international interest in understanding both everyday language use and reflection upon it by language users has grown. Scholars carving out a subdiscipline called *folk linguistics* have emphasized the importance of examining the discrepancies between what speakers say about their language use on the one hand and their actual linguistic behavior on the other. As Günthner, 2003, 192 (translation Perrin) put it: “[...] there are big differences between what speakers say about how they use language and how they actually use it [...].”

An example from public discourse that illustrates this discrepancy is the issue of inventing quotes in journalism. Professional ethics prohibit journalists from distorting their sources’ utterances or inventing source statements. In a large survey of Swiss journalists, none of them clicked the *yes* box following the question *Have you ever made up a quote?* However, an ethnography in the same community of practice showed that many journalists do invent quotes to support their storylines, often subconsciously (Haapanen & Perrin, 2018).

Another example of the discrepancy between practitioners’ self-conception and their actual use is writing in finance. In a transdisciplinary project on financial literacy, none of the interviewed financial analysts complained about any lack of writing skills. Only after realizing that even their colleagues from the office next door in the same banking department failed to understand their financial reports did they become aware of their lack of competence and potential ways to overcome it. As one analyst put it: “I was not aware that writing can be practiced.” (Whitehouse, 2022)*

Practicing an appropriate, purposeful use of language is precisely what the ancient discipline of rhetoric has emphasized for thousands of years. While focusing on oral language in real-life contexts, it prepared the ground for grammar studies, which were predominantly oriented toward written language and tended toward normative top-down approaches. Conversation Analysis, in the second half of the last century, turned back to real-life text production of oral language, followed by empirical writing research that has done the same for written language (Perrin, 2013b).

Investigating language – be it oral, written or transmodal – as a complex, situated practice in everyday contexts has contributed to a more nuanced understanding of language usage and change (Preston, 2016). This includes studying language users' awareness of what they do and why they do it. By exploring the differences between perceived and actual language use, researchers can gain deeper insights into language behavior and its implications for literacy, for communication, and for TD approaches to improve communication attempts within and across domains.

b) Two complementary cultures of literacy research

Literacy research is characterized by two complementary cultures. In the research on writing and reading, American studies have tended to rely on interview data to explore the social structures influencing everyday and professional literacy (e.g., Brandt, 2014). In contrast, German, Dutch, and Belgian studies have focused on data on activities of language use, such as logging the keystrokes of writers in the lab (e.g., de Smet, Leijten, & Van Waes, 2018) or in real-life contexts (Perrin, 2019). In both cases, what cannot be found directly in the data has to be reconstructed based on assumptions.

For example, American studies in the research on writing in the workplace and in everyday life tend to interpret information from interviews as hints to what a person did while writing. Before delivering her keynote at the 50th anniversary of the Writing Center at Dartmouth College in 2016, Deborah Brand was introduced with the words “[she] collects and comparatively analyzes in-depth, retrospective life interviews with everyday people to explore the social structures and processes [!] that bear on literacy and its changing conditions and meanings over time.”

In the same year, another international event on writing research took place not far from Dartmouth College in Hanover, NH, at the MIT in Boston, MA. Scholars from Western Europe drew their findings on activity data from recordings of writing processes. An exemplary workshop held by Mariëlle Leijten and Luuk Van Waes was entitled “Using Keystroke Logging in Writing Research”. *Keystroke logging* means that software beyond writers’ text editors records every keystroke and mouse or trackpad movement with a timestamp and a detailed activity protocol.

This timestamped activity protocol allows for a detailed reconstruction of the writing process, keystroke by keystroke, millisecond by millisecond. Researchers know exactly what a writer did – if it happened on screen. What keystroke data cannot tell us directly is why the writers processed their emerging text the way they did. By contrast, interview data can reveal writers’ repertoires of conscious reconstructions of their activity on more general levels and of text production strategies: what do I usually do when I write, and why do I do it this way?

Taken together, the complementary approaches could provide a comprehensive view of literacy. Interview-based studies offer rich, qualitative insights into individuals’ experiences and perceptions, while activity-based research provides detailed, quantitative data on actual literacy practices. Systematically combining these approaches promises to enhance the overall understanding of literacy development and its social implications. Interestingly, the two research lines have long remained unconnected, with only few exceptions.

c) French research line of Genetic Criticism

One of the rare comprehensive approaches to investigating real-life writing processes on micro and macro levels is termed *Genetic Criticism* (GC). However, in contrast to the two research lines presented above, GC analyzes writing processes that happened decades or centuries ago. The approach was developed in response to the acquisition of Heinrich Heine’s manuscripts by the Paris National Library in 1966. “[...] a research group was commissioned to analyze these manuscripts. First of all, an appropriate method had to be developed – GC.” (Grésillon & Perrin, 2014, 83)

On the micro level, GC considers all the physical traces on a manuscript as data. On the one hand, this includes the state of the material that carries the writing:

scratches, scraped spots, ink stains, fingerprints, and even traces of radioactive decay in the ink used are considered. On the other hand, the writing itself is analyzed, as a constellation of insertions and strikethroughs over time, of verbal and nonverbal signs, as well as of text body, metacommunicative comments, and graphic notes. The microdata is used to reconstruct the process in as much detail as possible.

On the macro level, the written text and related satellite texts from or to the same author are read for indications of the multi-layered context in which the literary text under investigation emerged. Layers include the situations in which the text was produced, the circumstances of the author's life, the uptake by readers as anticipated in the text, and the state of society at the time of writing. Contextual knowledge generated based on the manuscript data is then compared with historical knowledge on further circumstances surrounding the text production.

A particular focus of GC is on creativity in the literary text production process. The analyses provide a unique perspective on the creative process of experienced and successful literary artists. By examining the emergence of literary manuscripts, researchers can uncover the iterative and developmental nature of professional writing in a demanding and prestigious field. Beyond explaining writing in this very specific field, GC offers fundamental insights into the interplay of material, cognitive, and procedural aspects of text production that could matter to other fields, too.

Yet, the main particularity of GC, from a writing researcher's perspective, is its ex-post approach. If it were about investigating professional writing in general, GC would be far too complicated and expensive an endeavor. Why should researchers put resources into analyzing the radioactivity of ink on a two-hundred-year-old manuscript to reconstruct the sequence of revisions in a text if it was not about these specific pieces of art written by these outstanding authors? Due to its rigorous focus on reconstructing processes, however, GC has played a catalytic role in writing research.

d) German call for Progression Analysis

In the programmatic introduction to their volume on the then new field of text production research, Gerd Antos and Hans Peter Krings first discussed the relevance of GC for a procedural understanding of the dynamics of language use in text production. Then, they stated that the “analysis of text emergence [...]

is an approach which is, in principle, feasible and worthwhile for non-literary texts too. [...]. Empirical analyses of text geneses would make an important contribution to a clearly linguistically motivated text theory” (Antos, 1989, 36, translation Perrin).

I read this statement as a call for action and decided to move forward. Drawing on both academic and professional experience in information technologies and journalism, I used my PhD work to develop a methodology and a set of computational tools to investigate the text production processes of professionals working at their computers. In line with Antos’ call, I shifted the focus from ex-post to in-situ data generation and analyses. The goal was to investigate writers as they write in their real-life contexts, with as little impact as possible on the processes investigated.

I called the resulting multi-method approach *Progression Analysis* (PA). It is meant to enable researchers to develop empirically based reconstructions of what writers in context do when they write and why they do it in this way. Thus, PA includes three levels of analysis: a) the natural writing environment, b) writers’ activity at the interface of their computer, and c) their mental representation of this activity in context. Whereas the analysis on level a) draws on established methods from ethnography, levels b) and c) can be seen as cases of “technography” (Jansen & Vellema, 2011).

Writers’ activity on level b) is recorded using custom-made software for keystroke logging, which means that everything writers do on their computers is recorded (see above, Part 3.a). The logging software runs beyond a writer’s or an organization’s text editing system, of course without interferences. Whereas the software must be customized for each new recording environment, the format of the data has been standardized and kept consistent from the very beginning. This allows for long-term analyses and comparisons across research projects, workplaces, and domains.

Once a writer has implemented the new text, for example by submitting it to an editorial system in a newsroom, research shifts from level b) to level c). Now that the writing itself is over, a researcher shows the writer a real-time recording of the text production process. This recording was generated automatically, based on the data from level b). The researchers ask the writers to comment, while watching, on what they did and why they did it. The result is a cue-based retrospective verbal protocol of what the writers remember about the decisions they made while writing.

e) Extended Progression Analysis

It goes without saying that such data generation technology can be considered the mother of all spyware in settings such as newsrooms or financial analysts' workplaces. So why would practitioners allow researchers to install keystroke logging software and why would they participate in video-recorded sessions where they watch their writing processes in real time, sometimes for hours, and comment on what they did and why they did it? The most natural way to open these windows into practitioners' activities and minds is to raise their interest in the research results.

This loops back to the core idea of transdisciplinarity: academic researchers and practitioners collaborate on par to solve wicked problems (see above, Part 1.b). If the solution does benefit the practitioners, they have good reason to participate with their time and knowledge in a TD project. This raises the question of how they know in advance whether the outcomes will be worth the effort. TD collaboration is based on mutual trust and researchers' reputation in the practical field under investigation. This reputation can only be built over time, step by step.

Developing a plan to build a reputation as a researcher who deserves practitioners' trust was part of my PhD thesis. Besides three case studies using Progression Analysis, it included a masterplan for TD research in public discourse. The core idea of this plan was to increase both the size and the complexity of the research from project to project, while showcasing the practical relevance of the outcomes after each project not only in academia, but also in the communities of practice and society at large. The master plan could be implemented in a series of research projects that build on each other (Figure 4).

- Reflecting journalists' perspectives on newswriting:
Focused Ethnography | the SDA project | 1995–1998
- Learning from experienced writers:
+ Grounded Theory | the OFCOM project | 1997–2000
- Sharing knowledge with experts in newsrooms:
+ Transdisciplinary Action Research | the TA project | 1999–2001
- Raising awareness of a preexisting world:
+ Realist Social Theory | the Idée Suisse project | 2005–2010

- Understanding emergence in news flows:
+ Dynamic Systems Theory | the Modeling Writing Phase project | 2010–2013
- Shifting the integrative focus to new fields:
+ Argumentation Theory | the Argupolis project | 2012–2015
- Widening the semiotic angle:
+ Data Visualization Theory | the Indvil project | 2017–2019
- Reconstructing 30 years of digital literacy shift:
+ Artificial Intelligence in public discourse | the Ambizione project | 2024–2029

Figure 4. Series of research projects investigating professional text production

Figure 4 shows that, from project to project, PA was combined with more demanding research questions and more complex combinations of research frameworks. The Argupolis project, which included argumentation analysis, was the direct foundation for the PhD school collaboration with the USI team specialized in argumentation analysis. From project to project, the funding amount grew up to EUR 1 million for the latest project, reflecting and enabling the growing size and complexity of the projects and the teams involved.

The extended PA project design approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of writing as discourse production in context. By integrating complementary methods, researchers capture a holistic view of writing activities and the factors that influence them. The depth of understanding is crucial for developing targeted interventions to improve writing practices in TD collaboration. At the same time, such projects are strong generators of PhD spin-off projects that can, for example, focus on re-analyzing the data for special purposes. This is what facilitated the launch of our PhD programs.

4. Institutionalization: Developing a series of transdisciplinary PhD programs in Applied Linguistics

Investigating real-life language use on individual, organizational, and societal levels is one academic challenge; making this research a solid ground for PhD programs is another. We moved from conducting transdisciplinary research projects to implementing transdisciplinary PhD programs in five steps: aligning the initiatives of complementary academic institutions (a); outlining long-term perspectives for transdisciplinary collaboration (b); and using the shared language developed in research (c) to identify hotspots (d) for coordinated PhD research (e).

a) Aligning initiatives

Collaboration across academic institutions such as disciplines and universities often starts bottom-up, based on scholars' initiatives. This was the starting point of our PhD collaboration, too. However, there was a strategic argument for the institutionalization of these tactical initiatives from the very beginning: the universities and professorships involved complemented each other in terms of disciplinary background and transdisciplinary orientation, which improved our joint profiles for securing funding for socially promising research. This is mirrored in the three examples of joint research projects:

The goal of the *Idée Suisse* project (2005–2010) was to find out how Swiss public service media were able to fulfil their public mandate in an increasingly competitive environment. This mandate requires the public service media to foster social cohesion in Switzerland across linguistic regions and social strata. Results based on Progression Analysis (see above, Part 3.e) in a transdisciplinary framework (Part 1.b) showed that and how some experienced journalists managed to fulfill the mandate by reaching large audiences with politically relevant information.

The Argupolis newsroom project (2012–2015) took this idea further, with a strong theoretical focus on the interplay of argumentative and narrative strategies identified in the ethnographically gathered data. The *Idée Suisse* project group from ZHAW and the Universities of Bern (UniBe) and Lausanne (UniL) was expanded to include argumentation researchers from the University of Lugano (USI). Moreover, the USI researchers gathered and analyzed new data from Italian-speaking newsrooms, in addition to the German and French data from *Idée Suisse*.

At this stage of collaboration, ZHAW with its focus on Applied Linguistics and transdisciplinarity, had established stable connections with research teams from the three universities in three linguistic regions of Switzerland. These teams' research foci complement the ZHAW team's focus on text production research, ethnography, and transdisciplinarity in Applied Linguistics: the UniBe team focuses on sociolinguistics to investigate inequalities, the UniL team on interactional linguistics, and the USI team is well-versed in theoretically based analyses of argumentation in context.

Another large research project, Modeling Writing Phase (2010–2013), reanalyzed data from Progression Analyses collected in the previous projects. The goal was to automatically identify recurrent patterns of writing behavior based on Dynamic Systems Theory (see above, Part 1.e). The main cooperation partners were ZHAW and UniBe, the latter brought in sociolinguistic aspects – and formally supervised the PhD student in the project team. For doctorates, ZHAW, as a university of applied sciences, is to collaborate with classical universities in joint programs.

b) Outlining long-term perspectives

After co-supervising PhD students in many projects case by case, the teams involved welcomed a competitive initiative launched in 2015 by the umbrella organization of Swiss universities. This initiative invited Swiss universities of applied sciences, such as ZHAW, to develop PhD programs together with classical universities in Switzerland. Goals included broadening access to doctorates for students who had received their MA degree at a university of applied sciences – and fostering the practical relevance of PhD theses without compromising on their theoretical rigor.

From the very beginning, it was predictable that after a first funding period, 2016–2020, a second and perhaps even a third could be launched. This is why the team eligible for an Applied Linguistics program decided to outline a series of potential applications that build upon each other. The idea was to start with a very focused topic at the intersection field of ZHAW and one partner university, USI, and then gradually increase transdisciplinarity by shifting and widening both the topical scope and the group of collaboration partners. For the topical development, we outlined three axes:

- From the USI strength of analyzing argumentation toward investigating more complex modes of language use in real-life contexts: the first PhD program combined the rigor of theoretically grounded argumentation analysis (USI) with the social relevance of analyzing language use in real-life settings, related to real-life problems (ZHAW). The lessons learnt from this foundational step toward transdisciplinarity could then be used to extend into multimodality and linguistic modes beyond argumentation at the end of this first PhD program and in the subsequent one(s).
- From finance and public discourse toward other domains of language use: the first students enrolled in the first PhD program analyzed language use in domains where USI and ZHAW had gained analytical experience and established transdisciplinary networks. From there, the foci of PhD theses – and their supervision – could shift toward new application fields, such as social integration, societal cohesion, migration, and diversity. This strategic plan included setting up, at ZHAW and in close collaboration with UniBe, a BA and an MA program in linguistic integration and diversity management.
- From the human use and analyses of language use toward big data and artificial intelligence as both the object of research and a means of doing research: the first program clearly focused on language use by humans only and on applying classical methods of language analysis, mainly detailed analyses of text products or text production processes (see above, Part 3.b). Big data analyses and human-machine interaction on the one hand as well as the resulting digital divide on the other were planned to be foregrounded in a second and a third PhD program respectively.

c) Anchoring transdisciplinarity in a shared language

After completing many transdisciplinary projects as researchers, the PhD project team was able to build on the experience of developing shared languages. Why does this matter? Members of different academic fields tend to use different concepts when referring to similar entities of their shared reality. This applies even more so to members of non-academic professional communities. This is why transdisciplinary projects start from finding epistemological and linguistic common ground, a process which has been termed “developing shared languages” (Whitehouse, Rahm, & Wozniak, 2021).

Applied linguists are in a good position to foster this process, given their knowledge of intercultural communication, language policymaking, and language teaching and learning. Transforming this knowledge from the field and, most of all, from a solid experience of joint research projects and conveying it to the PhD students was defined as one of the main goals in the PhD school projects. When they first started conducting transdisciplinary research, they came to understand that, for teams with mixed epistemological backgrounds, shared concepts are key to mutual learning.

Another language-related success factor was the openness of the programs to multilingualism. Switzerland is a highly multilingual country, even on the level of official languages, with universities in three of its linguistic regions. Cooperating across universities and linguistic regions turned out to be a door opener in the application and funding process and a facilitator when carrying out the programs. In multilingual teams of PhD students, the need to develop shared languages for transdisciplinary collaboration and the analysis of multilingual data became a matter of course.

However, as argued above, even if all participants speak the same natural language, transdisciplinary research always results in linguistic issues. Academics, practitioners under investigation, and society at large speak different varieties. In our series of PhD programs, we have particularly aimed to attract students with professional backgrounds in both academia and the professional world they intend to investigate. These students are in good positions to operate as mediators between stakeholders' linguistic varieties and as catalysts for developing a shared language for their projects.

Finally, the series of PhD programs fostered intercultural communication and the development of common languages on the meta level of building joint academic institutions. The funding scheme suggested by the umbrella organization of Swiss universities implies that universities of applied sciences and classical universities are cooperation partners on par when developing this new type of PhD program. This encouraged both parties to stop talking and walking past each other and to develop shared epistemes of transdisciplinary collaboration instead – in our case with sustainable success.

d) Identifying hotspots for research

The three PhD programs, which were developed between 2015 and 2024, are the result of strategic planning. From the very beginning, long-term perspectives were discussed, and lines of development were defined (see above, Part 4.a). However, the master plan included the openness to adjust the finer planning along the way, depending on the developments in the academic and professional fields as well as in the partnering universities. This rolling planning led to the following development of the focus areas for the three PhD programs.

- The first program, 2015–2020, was entitled *Argumentation in Professional Practice*. The main university partners were ZHAW and USI. Students and teachers from additional universities in Switzerland and from abroad joined the program. The main goal was to develop an institutional platform for transdisciplinary PhD projects. Focussing on written argumentation as the main linguistic mode under investigation helped the two universities advance on solid, well-explored ground: argumentation from USI along with writing and transdisciplinarity from ZHAW.
- The second program, 2020–2025, built on the same platform but broadened the scope: *Managing Languages, Arguments, and Narratives in the Datafied Society*. The focus of PhD theses arising from this program scaled up from producing argumentative (written) language to managing any form of language use that combined argumentation with linguistic modes such as narration – which is the default case in real-life communication. In addition, big data started to matter, both as a prerequisite for AI applications and as a challenge when dealing with research data.
- The third program, 2025–2028, is called *Equilingua: Linguistic Diversity and Social Justice in the Digital Transformation*. The main context for the PhD theses to be developed in this program is the digitalization of language use and communication. Against this rapidly changing technological and economical backdrop, the focus is on social aspects such as linguistic diversity, digital literacies and divides, as well as empowerment. Applied Linguistics is combined with studies in intercultural communication, accessibility, media literacy, and human–machine interaction.

For this third program, ZHAW switched partners from USI to UniBe. The funding policy requires universities of applied sciences intending to submit a third application for a PhD program to launch both a new partnership and a fresh

topic. UniBe with its sociolinguistic focus is an ideal partner for a program on linguistic diversity and social justice, just as USI was for argumentation in professional practice. Taken together, the two cooperative projects and three PhD programs offered unique opportunities to systematically explore transdisciplinarity in increasingly complex settings.

e) Co-ordinating PhD research

Preparing these organizational settings has been a long-term challenge for the universities and scholars involved. As a university of applied sciences mainly funded by the Swiss universities' umbrella organization, ZHAW needed to ensure that their Master's program in Applied Linguistics enables students to enter a PhD program that requires theoretical and methodological rigor on the level of classical universities' curricula. Conversely, classical universities have had to overcome any prejudice against universities of applied sciences and collaboration with practitioners on par.

The umbrella organization of Swiss universities funded each program (see above, Part 4.b) by supporting three types of activity: first, teachers' lectures and workshops; second, students' conference participation and open access publications; and third, the project teams' development of sustainable teaching and learning materials. This third type of financing has strongly contributed to the success of the PhD program series. The resulting MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) and other materials have enabled students with variegated backgrounds to join the program and start on common ground.

Moreover, comprehensive supervision of transdisciplinary theses had to be ensured. We did that by composing a board of experts excelling in both disciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches. Regular board meetings have ensured close collaboration among supervisors across universities, disciplines, and domains. Other measures to strengthen the quality of the transdisciplinary PhD projects included workshops in which the PhD students discuss their research projects with stakeholders ranging from academics to professional practitioners and society at large.

Launching the programs has included concise messages to potential students, such as: "In our PhD school, we analyze language and languages used in a world increasingly driven by artificial intelligence. We focus on arguments and narratives as fundamental modes of human sensemaking through language and their

multilayered interplay in educational, professional, and public discourse in the current datafied societies. Our goal is to identify the value humans can add to artificial intelligence in datafied societies and their increasingly algorithmic practices of language processing.”^{xi}

The PhD courses themselves have addressed their topics by combining three levels of multidisciplinary (Figure 5): the disciplinarity of Applied Linguistics and neighboring disciplines, drawing on their theoretical and methodological developments; interdisciplinarity with AI research, foregrounding technological developments for language use and language research; and transdisciplinarity with experts from academic and professional fields, focusing on potential human and social value added to AI-driven language use and research.

Figure 5. Visualization of the second PhD program's multidisciplinary

5. Three exemplary PhD theses: Financial literacy, trust building, and skeptical pandemic discourse

Scaling up transdisciplinary research to real-life communication has resulted in the series of the three PhD programs explained above: the first one on *Argumentation in Professional Practice*; the second on *Managing Languages, Arguments and Narratives in the Datafied Society*; and the third on *Linguistic Diversity and Social Justice in the Digital Transformation* (a). Exemplary theses from these programs investigate financial literacy (b), startup communication (c), and skeptical pandemic discourse (d). Their variegated transdisciplinary aspects have proven to be door openers (e).

a) Three PhD programs to grow expertise

The series of our three PhD programs funded by the Swiss universities' umbrella organization has been characterized by shifts on the layers of universities involved, theories and methods foregrounded, modes of language use under research, and practical fields addressed (see above, Part 4.d). But most importantly, our expertise in enabling and evaluating PhD theses with transdisciplinary aspects has grown within and across the programs. As a result, more and more students without previous TD knowledge have decided to gain TD experience during their PhD project.

In the first program, supporting TD research on the level of a PhD thesis was novel to the universities involved. While everybody in the PhD school team was experienced in doing inter- or even transdisciplinary research themselves, we had never broken it down to the level of systematically enabling students to combine disciplinary rigor with transdisciplinary inclusiveness. Instead, the first TD projects launched in this program benefitted from the PhD student's quasi-simultaneous double career in academia and the practical world under research (see below, Part 5.b).

The second program drew on this experience and the traces of the pioneering work in the first program. These traces include curricular modules and teaching materials on the academic challenges of going deep and broad at the same time as a researcher. Both the modules and the materials helped new PhD students build the knowledge needed for thorough academic research in real-life settings. Thus, the second program was strong in enabling expert practitioners (who had

completed their studies a long time ago) to return to doing research (see below, Part 5.c).

The third program, finally, has benefitted from preparatory curricular work at ZHAW: a Bachelor’s and a Master’s program in the thematic field of the third PhD program, linguistic diversity, had been established during the first two PhD programs. The network with the practical world, developed for and in the BA and MA programs, is now open for the PhD program, too. This means that students strongly rooted in academic approaches to linguistic diversity but with little practical background or network, can easily access real-world settings in the field (see below, Part 5.d).

Taken together, the three programs neatly build upon each other. The first program started from the (rare) case of a student with a double career – a dream profile for TD research. The second program included TD-specific academic booster courses, while the third one has integrated a TD-specific network of practitioners with an affinity for research. In sum, what the present PhD program offers differs decisively from what students can expect in a disciplinary PhD context. It includes alumni from our first programs sharing their exemplary expertise with our new students.

b) PhD thesis 1: Transdisciplinarity thought through

An exemplary PhD thesis from the first PhD program investigates the communicative potential of financial analysts’ texts. The research focuses on, first, identifying the reasons behind the current state of these texts and, second, exploring how analysts can achieve different target states if necessary. The thesis builds on the empirically grounded assumption that improving the clarity and effectiveness of financial communication can foster trust and facilitate informed decision-making in society, addressing issues related to low financial literacy.^{xii}

Starting in 2017, the author, MW, aimed at answering the following research question: what are the reasons for the actual state of texts, and how can financial analysts reach a different target state if necessary? In the interview data, a financial analyst says that he “was not aware that writing can be practiced”. In the thesis, MW shows that systematically improving the communicative potential of financial analysts’ texts can foster trust building and facilitate informed decision-making on financial matters among society, enabling the masses to participate in the financial markets, despite low financial literacy.

Identifying a socially relevant problem of language use, understanding it from the perspectives of the main stakeholders, developing a theoretically and practically sound solution, implementing it, and measuring its effects in real-life contexts means walking the entire TD talk (see above, Part 1.b) in one single thesis. The table of contents of the thesis mirrors this trajectory from formulating the research question to discussing the “added value of the research-based interventions” (Figure 6). The international PhD committee awarded the thesis *summa cum laude*.

Part I – Problem Identification	1 Overall Research Question
	2 Transdisciplinary Framework
	3 Research Architecture
Part II – Problem Analysis	4 Context Perspective
	5 Product Perspective
	6 Process Perspective
	7 Integration of the Results
Part III – Problem Solution	8 Diagnosis: Research-Based Approaches for Measures
	9 Intervention: Coaching, Training, Organisational Development
	10 Added Value of Research-Based Interventions
	11 Taking Stock – the Overall Conclusion
References	
Appendices	

Figure 6. ToC of the transdisciplinary thesis by MW, blue part on knowledge transformation

The Swiss National Science Foundation supported the open access publication of the thesis at Palgrave MacMillan’s (Whitehouse, 2023). Since its publication, the OA book has been accessed more than ten thousand times. MW was invited to co-edit a handbook on professional literacy at Mouton de Gruyter’s and to join the board of the International Association of Business Communication. Among the invitations for chairs at several universities, she decided in favor of the one on professional literacy at ZHAW. She investigates and teaches professional literacy at her home base and abroad.

When explaining her field of research to academics across disciplines, she says: “Professional literacy [...] enables individual agents and their organizations to exploit linguistic processes and use language products to communicate adequately with and participate successfully in their community of practice and society at large.”^{xiii} In a TEDx talk, she tells laypeople “how communication in our society based on the division of labor can be improved by research-based coaching. We need a world where experts integrate the needs of their addressees in their communication.”^{xiv}

c) PhD thesis 2: Collaborating with non-collaborative practitioners

The thesis used as an example for the second PhD program examines the linguistic drivers of a mobility startup's rise and fall. In 2020, the company Nikola skyrocketed and then collapsed on the stock markets. In 2022, its founder was sentenced for dishonest communication.^{xv} Nikola's rise and fall attracted attention worldwide. The media criticized the founder's communicative practices as the main cause of failure. The thesis aimed at digging deeper by analyzing these practices and deriving empirically grounded guidelines for "building trust in startup communication".^{xvi}

The author, MB, started writing his thesis in early 2020, defended it in late 2023, and published it open access at Springer's in 2024. In line with the PhD program's theme, *Managing Languages, Arguments and Narratives in the Datafied Society*, MB analyzed publicly accessible databases for arguments and narratives in the discourse on the Nikola case. He did so after interrelating the states of research in argumentation theory and narratology and developing a theoretically grounded analytical framework to examine the interplay of argumentation and narration in startup communication.

Developing this framework as a substantial contribution to discourse analysis was the most demanding part for MB after a decade of practice in the language and communication industry. He has held senior management positions at Swiss National TV and worked as a communication consultant in his own company. Close collaboration with his academic supervisors in the PhD years helped him reload and further develop the academic mindset rooted in his studies of economics and communications in the nineties. In the end, his contribution was well received by all its stakeholders.

The thesis closes on the notion that it "may provide fertile ground on which to build new research that contributes to our understanding of startup communication and trust formation" (Born, 2024, 233). In the view of the international PhD committee, it does. They considered MB's thesis a *summa cum laude* contribution to academic work. According to MB, the frequent discussions with colleagues in the PhD school and the constant feedback from his supervisors helped him find his way back to scientific rigor while keeping an eye on practical requirements and expectations.

From a TD perspective, the consequences of the thesis are remarkable. MB now teaches "Multimodal Argumentative Storytelling" at several universities and

advises key institutions of public discourse on this practically crucial, but so far surprisingly little researched, topic. In a nutshell: it took an informed transdisciplinary approach to weave the research lines of two traditional academic fields – argumentation theory and narratology – together with the dynamics of real-life communication in situations where private and public interests clash.

d) PhD thesis 3: From inter- to transdisciplinary research practice

The third example of a PhD thesis was started in the second and finalized in the third PhD program. It uses Grounded Theory (see above, Part 1.e) to analyze pointing practices in the skeptical pandemic discourse in German-speaking Switzerland. The dataset consisted of an annotated text corpus of 107 skeptical websites, comprising 18,868 texts (15,108,308 words). *Pointing* refers to the frequent use of hyperlinks, bibliographical referencing, and citing. The analysis maps directions (who points at whom) and functions (legitimization, community building ...) of pointing practices.

This may sound rather abstract for a PhD thesis in the context of transdisciplinarity. On closer inspection, understanding the roles of deixis and hypertextuality in public discourse can contribute to solving a socially relevant problem in which language use plays a crucial role (see above, Part 1.a): how does social media shape our conception of reality and our decisions as citizens in, inter alia, increasingly undermined democracies? This third example of a PhD thesis therefore differs from the two previous ones in that the research question itself does not directly name the work's practical relevance.

Moreover, in contrast to the two previous cases, DD, the author of this thesis, looks back on a mostly academic trajectory: although he has worked as a translator, he does not have decades of experience as a practitioner in the professional field he is now investigating, namely public discourse on socially explosive topics. At the start of his PhD project in 2020, he was still fully involved in academic life. He earned his Master's degree in Applied Linguistics at the ZHAW in 2018 and has since been working as a research associate and lab coordinator^{xvii} at the same university.

In other words, DD's participation in the PhD program followed on seamlessly from his Bachelor's and Master's studies. It is only now that his path has started to lead him toward non-academic practice. On this path, he benefits from the structures established in the two previous PhD programs, in addition to the large

practical network of the third PhD program. Moreover, the focus of this program on the interplay of social structures, linguistic practices, and digital transformation brings him together with peers interested in discussing mechanisms of mediatized public discourse.

When asked about his view of the program, DD said: “In the PhD program, I acquire multidisciplinary knowledge and skills: I consolidate my disciplinary knowledge as a linguist, I get to know neighboring subject areas and people working in them and acquire interdisciplinary knowledge. I finally get to know different practical needs, forms of cooperation and mediation and, most importantly, practitioners. This helps me expand my transdisciplinary inventory. In my view, it is mainly through this multidisciplinaryity that research can be applied in a sustainable way.”^{xviii}

e) Patterns across individual theses

Taken together, the three theses outlined above illustrate transdisciplinary patterns of combining academic analyses with professional and societal needs. Be it fostering financial literacy, building trust in startup communication, or learning from social media practices in skeptical pandemic discourse – addressing wicked problems (see above, Part 1.b) requires access to practitioners’ situated activity, mindsets, and contextual resources. Starting from a solid knowledge base on field research helps researchers tackle the uncertainties of collaborating with practitioners on par.

As shown with the three exemplary theses, this knowledge base – throughout the three PhD programs – has included academically proven conceptualizations of text production and its investigation in real-life contexts. Extended Progression Analysis (see above, Part 3.e), argumentation theory and narratology, as well as sociolinguistic critical thinking (Part 4.a) help capture and understand what individuals and organizations do when they process communicational offers in their professional and everyday environments.

In all three theses and throughout the programs, PhD students have been encouraged and enabled to combine research frameworks and methods. Starting from deep case studies or broad corpus analyses, the analyses aim at combining emic and etic perspectives in ethnographies. They allow for theoretically sound generalization based on standards of Grounded Theory. Moreover, they include

elements of Integrative Social Theories and Dynamic Systems Theory to interrelate the observed linguistic dynamics with social change (Part 1.e).

The linguistic dynamics captured by the PhD research in our programs tend to be changes in the way people use (digital) media to process communicational offers. By providing empirical evidence of these changes, the researchers contribute to better understanding the digital literacy shift (Part 1.d) and its relevance for professions and society at large. They do so from various angles and in multitudes of domains of language use, but always based on a still-growing body of knowledge in a field – text production research in real-life contexts – that has long been under-researched.

The latency of academic work in this field can be explained methodologically: empirical studies *in* this complex and dynamic field require appropriate access *to* the field. The PhD researchers in our programs have experienced that practitioners tend to give deep access to their linguistic activities only if they can expect to get something back they consider practically relevant. This is, ultimately, why TD was developed (see above, Part 1.b). Our programs have enabled students to engage in TD-informed collaboration for and in their PhD research and theses.

Conclusion

This paper concludes by discussing transdisciplinary PhD programs' potential pitfalls and opportunities in times of science criticism and digital transformation. Based on ten years of experience in developing, managing, and evaluating such programs, the most concise summary is: we would do it again. Given Applied Linguistics' proximity to transdisciplinarity, it is easy to argue that socially relevant problems in which language plays a key role (AL) are best solved through research on, for, and with practitioners. Their expertise matters in the knowledge generation process.

However, mediating (AL!) between the languages, epistemes, and knowledge cultures of laypeople, language professionals, and language scholars requires particular attention in the research process (Maguire, 2015). And so does identifying positive deviants' tacit knowledge (TD!) in the practical world and making it available through knowledge transformation (Polanyi, 1966). This need for academic attention applies to doing Applied Linguistics research on, for, and with practitioners (see above, Part 1.a) – and even more so to guiding research in a transdisciplinary PhD program.

- From the perspective of research with practitioners, PhD students with TD projects need to learn to transgress and overcome boundaries on three levels: a) between domains such as science, education, and management; b) between disciplines such as AL and communication studies; and c) between institutions such as universities, NGOs, and businesses. Integrating (instead of excluding) all the relevant stakeholders throughout a project is a challenge that must be supported by the program's curriculum and network as well as in the form of the supervisors' experience and presence.
- From the perspective of research on practitioners, transdisciplinary theses must meet the quality standards of contributions to three discourses: academic discourse, professional discourse, and public discourse in society at large. PhD students therefore must understand and manage the “quadrangulation of disciplinary depth, multidisciplinary breadth, interdisciplinary integration, and transdisciplinary competencies” (Klein, 2008, 406). To prevent them from getting lost in endless work, they need guidance in academic project management.

- From the perspective of research for practitioners, finally, TD research ideally results in outcomes on three levels: “true” mid-range theories about situated activity as a contribution to theory building in academia, “authentic” insights into practices as a basis for measures in the professional domain investigated, and “prudent” measures to solve the wicked professional problems under investigation in a socially sustainable way (Kemmis, 1988, 46). This requires teaching research-based methods of knowledge transformation (Gravengaard, 2018) in the PhD curricula.

If the programs and the associated research combine these diverse and sometimes contradictory requirements and expectations, PhD students work harder than in a disciplinary thesis – simply because the TD part does not replace disciplinary rigor but complements it. In return for their extra work they are given the opportunity to immerse themselves in networked, multi-perspective thinking at a crucial stage of their career. Exposure to diverse viewpoints and collaborative practices can enhance their ability to address complex problems and develop innovative solutions.

Professions and society at large benefit from excellent transdisciplinary PhD work by gaining sustainable and actionable knowledge based on solid empirical evidence. In turn, academia can boost its reputation among society – and obtain empirically grounded knowledge on real-life matters on top. Thus, early-career researchers equipped with the necessary skills and perspectives to address complex real-world problems and make meaningful contributions to both academia and society are proving to be an embodied answer to anti-scientific criticism and disoriented fake news.

What it takes is considerable effort and a subtle paradigm shift within academia. It is in our hands.

Endnotes

- i For a concise discussion of the discrepancy between public interest and the crisis of confidence in the humanities and social sciences in Switzerland, yet in global and historical contexts, see Haller, 2024.
- ii For a critical discussion of this premise see, e.g., Hansson & Polk, 2018.
- iii My special thanks go to the students and lecturers of the PhD programs – as well as the colleagues with whom I had the chance to develop and lead the programs: Prof. Dr. Andrea Rocci, Dr. Eva Kuske, and Dr. Marta Zampa.
- iv AILA (2024). What is AILA, from <http://www.aila.info/about/index.htm>.
- v <https://gal-ev.de/> (author's translation).
- vi BAAL, the British Association of Applied Linguistics, is one of the founding members of AILA, the International Association of Applied Linguistics. However, the impetus to set up a worldwide organization came mainly from applied linguists in France. This is why the acronym AILA stands for its French name, Association Internationale de Linguistique Appliquée. <https://www.baal.org.uk/british-association-for-applied-linguistics/what-applied-linguistics-is-and-does/>
- vii Since the 1970 conference, the OECD has further expanded its commitment to transdisciplinary research (see, e.g., OECD, 2020).
- viii It does so even in academic publishing, see, e.g., Haider, Söderström, Ekström, & Rödl, 2024.
- ix The term hot topics is used, e.g., by AILA to feature their online research debate (<https://aila.info/research/debate/>).
- x Data set in Appendix D, statements from financial analysts, no. 055. Original in German: "Es war mir nicht klar, dass man Schreiben üben kann."
- xi <https://www.zhaw.ch/en/linguistics/study/doctoral-programmes/doctoral-programme-2021-2024/>
- xii United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 4.6.1, from <https://sdg.data.gov/4-6-1/>
- xiii Cited from the submitted proposal for the handbook (Whitehouse & McKenna, 2026, in prep.)
- xiv The TEDx video was published in April 2024 and generated more than 100k views in two weeks. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_vtF_qdVRcM
- xv In legal terms: In 2022, Nikola's founder was convicted of one count of securities fraud and two counts of wire fraud.
- xvi This is the title of both the PhD thesis and its published version (Born, 2024).
- xvii ZHAW Labs connect research with needs from professional practice and society at large by developing empirically sound solutions to practical problems. <https://www.zhaw.ch/en/linguistics/business-services/laic-lab/>
<https://www.zhaw.ch/de/ueber-uns/person/dago/>
- xviii Personal communication between the author of this paper and the author of the thesis, 2024-09-11.

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